

On the Photochemical Oxidation of Formaldehyde by Hydrogen Peroxide in Acid Medium with Tungstic Acid Sol as Photo-catalyst.

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In a previous communication from this laboratory, Ghosh and Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 231) have studied the photochemical oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide in acid medium, with tungstic acid sol as photo-catalyst. The results obtained were in many respects somewhat peculiar and it was thought desirable to study in greater detail the photochemical oxidation of formaldehyde in presence of tungstic acid sol.

It may be stated at the outset that the general features of the photo-oxidation of formaldehyde are very similar to that of glucose. As in the case of glucose, here also the conditions of experiment were so arranged that tungstic acid sol behaved as a pure photo-catalyst in the oxidation of formaldehyde by hydrogen peroxide. The other experimental precautions mentioned in the previous paper were also taken in this case.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Apparatus and experimental arrangement are same as in a previous paper. (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 911).

First of all, it was observed whether there was any decomposition of formaldehyde only in ultra-violet rays. Formaldehyde was estimated by titrating with iodine and sodium thiosulphate (*vide* Plimmer, "Practical Organic and Biochemistry," p.85).

It will be seen from the following table that formaldehyde does not decompose in ultra-violet rays.

TABLE I.

Conc. of formaldehyde.	Time.	C.c. of thiosulphate \equiv 3 c.c. H ² CHO + 20 c.c. iodine sol.
0.1149 M	0 hrs.	29.9
	2	29.9
	4	29.9
	0	29.5
0.01149 M	2	29.5
	4	29.45

Hydrogen peroxide (Merck's chemically pure "Perhydrol") in acid solution was then exposed to ultra-violet rays to see whether there was any decomposition. Kingzett's methods was adopted for the estimation of hydrogen peroxide.

Corning glass filter G.586 J (*vide* Technologic Papers of the Bureau of Standards, No. 148) was used for isolating the spectral region $430\mu\mu$ — $330\mu\mu$ in the violet and the ultra-violet. It was interposed between the reaction tube and the mercury lamp. With this glass filter, hydrogen peroxide in acid solution did not decompose.

Then a mixture of hydrogen peroxide, hydrochloric acid and formaldehyde was exposed to ultra-violet rays and Corning glass filter G.586 J interposed between reaction cell and mercury lamp. It will be seen from the following table that there is no decomposition.

Conc. of HCHO.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Time.	C.c. of thiosulphate ≡ 3 c. c. reaction mixture.
0.033 M	0.015 M	0.1N	0 min.	8.3 c.c.
			120	8.3
			180	8.3

Finally, a mixture of formaldehyde, hydrogen peroxide, hydrochloric acid and sodium tungstate was used. The hydrogen peroxide solution was freshly prepared before each day's experiment, as it decomposed in glass vessel after standing for some time. Radiations in the spectral region $430\mu\mu$ — $330\mu\mu$ have no action of hydrogen peroxide as such, but the ultra-violet light transmitted by this filter is very effective in bringing about the oxidation of formaldehyde by tungstic acid sol and hydrogen peroxide.

The reaction mixtures used in this investigation are given in the following tables. It will be noticed that the concentration of hydrochloric acid was never less than 0.075N. Sodium tungstate reacts with hydrochloric acid to form a sol according to the following equation:—

In our experiment, therefore, the molar concentration of tungstate was always less than two-thirds of the concentration of hydrochloric acid. The reaction mixtures were quite stable in the dark and no visible turbidity due to the coagulation of the tungstic acid sol occurred during the time of carrying out the experiments.

The hydrogen peroxide left over was estimated by Kingzett's method. In acid solution, the presence of formaldehyde does not affect the titration in the least.

That a mixture of formaldehyde, hydrogen peroxide, hydrochloric acid and sodium tungstate does not react in the dark, will be seen from the following table.

TABLE II.

Temp. of thermostat = 30°. Conc. of formaldehyde = 0.0287 *M*.
 Conc. of hydrogen peroxide = 0.02043 *M*. Conc. of sodium tungstate = 0.025 *M*.
 Conc. of hydrochloric acid = 0.0794 *N*. Conc. of thiosulphate = 0.01 *N*.

Time in min.	C.c. of thiosulphate = 3 c.c. reaction mixture.
0	12.9 c.c.
120	12.9
240	12.9

The experimental results for different concentrations of formaldehyde and hydrogen peroxide are recorded in Table IIa—IIc.

TABLE IIa.

Conc. of CH_2O .	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	k (unimolecular with respect to H_2O_2).
(a) 0.0287 <i>M</i>	0.01267 <i>M</i>	0.0794 <i>N</i>	0.0419 <i>N</i>	0.025 <i>M</i>	0.0026
(b) „	0.02043 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0025
(c) „	0.02290 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0024
(d) „	0.02585 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0020
(e) „	0.02710 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0010
(f) „	0.03452 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.00088

TABLE IIb.

(a) 0.0367 <i>M</i>	0.01590 <i>M</i>	0.0809 <i>N</i>	0.0434 <i>N</i>	0.025 <i>M</i>	0.0029
(b) „	0.02590 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0027
(c) „	0.02843 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0013
(d) „	0.04628 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.00049

TABLE IIc.

Conc. of CH_2O .	Conc. of H_2O_2 .	Conc. of HCl .	Conc. of free HCl	Conc. of tungstate.	k (unimolecular with respect to H_2O_2).
(a) 0.0685 M	0.0199 M	0.0787 N	0.0412 N	0.025 M	0.0030
(b) "	0.0255 M	"	"	"	0.0029
(c) "	0.0290 M	"	"	"	0.0020
(d) "	0.0439 M	"	"	"	0.00085

The experimental results given in Tables II(a), II(b) and II(c) are plotted graphically in Figure I. It will be noticed that the velocity constants diminish slowly at first, as the concentration of hydrogen peroxide increases. At about a concentration of hydrogen peroxide equivalent to the concentration of sodium tungstate, the curve suddenly shows a steep descent and then with further increase in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide becomes flat again.

FIG. I.

As the concentration of formaldehyde increases, the curves are pushed further and further from the point of origin, the curves for higher concentration of formaldehyde lying above the curve for the lower concentration, but the nature of the curve remains the same. It is also to be noted that for higher concentrations of hydrogen peroxide—concentrations greater than 5.026N—the velocity of reaction becomes almost zero-molecular. Of course, when the initial concentration of hydrogen peroxide is large and the total change is a small fraction of the initial concentration, it is difficult to decide exactly whether a reaction is zero-molecular or unimolecular, but in this case, there is unmistakable evidence that the reaction, with large increase in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide tends to be zero-molecular.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Formaldehyde.

TABLE III.

Temperature of thermostat = 32°.

Conc. of CH ₂ O.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	<i>k</i> .
(a) 0.0134 M	0.026 M	0.0787 N	0.0412 N	0.025 M	0.0011
(b) 0.0287 M	0.02585 M	0.0794 N	0.0419 N	„	0.0020
(c) 0.0685 M	0.0255 M	0.0787 N	0.0412 N	„	0.0029

TABLE IV.

Temperature of thermostat = 32°.

Conc. of CH ₂ O.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	<i>k</i> .
(a) 0.0287 M	0.02710 M	0.0794 N	0.0419 N	0.025 M	0.001
(b) 0.0357 M	0.02843 M	0.0809 N	0.0434 N	„	0.0013
(c) 0.0685 M	0.02900 M	0.0787 N	0.0412 N	„	0.002

When we plot graphically $1/k$ against $1/\text{conc. of formaldehyde}$, we see that there is a straight line (Fig. 2).

FIG. II.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of HCl.

TABLE V.

Temperature of thermostat = 32°.

Conc. of CH ₂ O.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	<i>k</i> .
0.0287 <i>M</i>	0.02585 <i>M</i>	0.0794 <i>N</i>	0.0419 <i>N</i>	0.025 <i>M</i>	0.002
0.0280 <i>M</i>	0.0255 <i>M</i>	0.2360 <i>N</i>	0.1990 <i>N</i>	„	0.0011

It will be seen that the unimolecular constant almost varies inversely as the square root of the concentration of free hydrochloric acid.

Effect of Varying the Concentration of Sodium Tungstate.

TABLE VI.

Temperature of thermostat = 32°.

Conc. of CH ₂ O.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	<i>k</i> .
0.028 <i>M</i>	0.0255 <i>M</i>	0.236 <i>N</i>	0.1990 <i>N</i>	0.0250 <i>M</i>	0.0011
„	0.0250 <i>M</i>	„	0.2172 <i>N</i>	0.0125 <i>M</i>	0.00099
„	„	„	0.2266 <i>N</i>	0.0063 <i>M</i>	0.00066
„	„	„	0.2305 <i>N</i>	0.0037 <i>M</i>	0.00060

The velocity constant diminishes as the concentration of sodium tungstate diminishes. It should be noted that in the experiments described above, the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is either equal or greater than that of sodium tungstate.

Effect of Varying the Temperature.

TABLE VII.

Temp. of thermostat.	Conc. of CH ₂ O.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	<i>k</i> .	Temp. coeff. $\frac{k_1 + 10}{k_2}$
32°	0.0287 <i>M</i>	0.03452 <i>M</i>	0.0794 <i>N</i>	0.0419 <i>N</i>	0.025 <i>M</i>	0.00083	
37°	0.0280 <i>M</i>	0.0357 <i>M</i>	0.0787 <i>N</i>	0.0412 <i>N</i>	„	0.00092	1.2
42° (calc.)	„	„	„	„	„	0.0010	
32°	0.0685 <i>M</i>	0.035 <i>M</i>	0.0787 <i>N</i>	0.0412 <i>N</i>	„	0.0018	
37°	„	0.0357 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.0021	1.270
42° (calc.)	„	„	„	„	„	0.0024	
32°	0.0287 <i>M</i>	0.02043 <i>M</i>	0.0794 <i>N</i>	0.0419 <i>N</i>	„	0.0025	
37°	0.0280 <i>M</i>	0.0207 <i>M</i>	0.0787 <i>N</i>	0.0412 <i>N</i>	„	0.0029	1.34
42° (calc.)	„	„	„	„	„	0.0033	

The temperature coefficient is small, being of the order of 1.2—1.3.

Effect of Varying the Intensity of Radiation.

TABLE VIII.

Temperature of thermostat = 32°.

Intensity of radiation. (in ergs. per sq. cm. per sec.).	Conc. of CH ₂ O.	Conc. of H ₂ O ₂ .	Conc. of HCl.	Conc. of free HCl.	Conc. of tungstate.	<i>k</i> .
1512	0.0287 <i>M</i>	0.03452 <i>M</i>	0.0794 <i>N</i>	0.0419 <i>N</i>	0.025 <i>M</i>	0.00083
785	0.028 <i>M</i>	0.035 <i>M</i>	0.0787 <i>N</i>	0.0412 <i>N</i>	„	0.00061
1512	0.028 <i>M</i>	0.0357 <i>M</i>	0.236 <i>N</i>	0.199 <i>N</i>	„	0.00054
785	„	0.035 <i>M</i>	„	„	„	0.00051
1512	0.0685 <i>M</i>	0.035 <i>M</i>	0.0787 <i>N</i>	0.0412 <i>N</i>	„	0.0018
785	„	„	„	„	„	0.0013

It will be seen from Table VIII that for free acid strength 0.04*N*, the velocity constants vary as the square root of intensity of incident radiation; but when the concentration of free hydrochloric acid is large, the velocity constant varies only very slightly with increase in the intensity of radiation.

The intensity of ultra-violet radiations, absorbed by the reacting systems after passing through a Corning glass filter G.586 J and a rectangular quartz vessel filled with water at constant temperature was measured by a Moll thermopile and galvanometer. The quantum efficiencies are recorded in Table IX.

TABLE IX.

Quantum efficiency : calculated from	Composition of reaction mixture.	Quantum effi- ciency.
(1) <i>f</i> in Table IIa	0.0287 <i>M</i> -HCHO + 0.03452 <i>M</i> -H ₂ O ₂ + 0.0794 <i>N</i> -HCl + 0.025 <i>M</i> -tungstate.	3
(2) <i>d</i> „	0.02585 <i>M</i> -H ₂ O ₂ . All other factors same as in (1).	4.7
(3) <i>b</i> in Table IIb	0.0357 <i>M</i> -HCHO + 0.0259 <i>M</i> -H ₂ O ₂ + 0.0809 <i>N</i> -HCl + 0.025 <i>M</i> -tungstate.	7.2
(4) <i>d</i> „	0.04628 <i>M</i> -H ₂ O ₂ . All other factors same as in (3).	2.4
(5) <i>a</i> in Table III	0.0134 <i>M</i> -HCHO + 0.0260 <i>M</i> -H ₂ O ₂ + 0.0787 <i>N</i> -HCl + 0.025 <i>M</i> -tungstate.	2.76
(6) <i>d</i> in Table IV	0.0685 <i>M</i> -HCHO + 0.0787 <i>N</i> -HCl + 0.025 <i>M</i> -tungstate + 0.020 <i>M</i> -H ₂ O ₂ .	3.4

Discussion of Experimental Results.

Any mechanism of reaction that may be proposed for this photochemical oxidation should be in a position to explain the following facts:—

(1) The velocity of reaction with reference to hydrogen peroxide is monomolecular at lower concentrations of hydrogen peroxide, but tends to become zero-molecular as the initial concentration of hydrogen peroxide increases.

(2) With increase in the initial concentration of hydrogen peroxide keeping the concentration of sodium tungstate fixed at 0.025 *M*, the velocity constant slowly diminishes, but when a concentration of hydrogen peroxide, almost equal to that of sodium tungstate is reached, the velocity constant diminishes very rapidly (Fig. 1).

(3) The velocity constant is inversely proportional to the concentration of hydrogen ion.

(4) The velocity constant increases slightly as the concentration of formaldehyde is increased.

(5) Provided the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is equal to or greater than that of sodium tungstate, the velocity constant diminishes as the concentration of sodium tungstate diminishes.

(6) For smaller concentrations of free hydrochloric acid, the velocity constant varies as the square root of the intensity of incident radiation; but for higher acid concentrations, the variation of velocity constant with intensity is much smaller.

(7) Two to seven molecules of formaldehyde undergo oxidation for each quantum of light absorbed.

(8) Temperature coefficient of the velocity of reaction is small.

It is obvious that the central feature of the reaction is indicated by the very rapid fall in the value of the velocity constant when the initial concentration of hydrogen peroxide becomes almost equivalent to that of sodium tungstate. The only possible satisfactory explanation of this remarkable fact lies in assuming that tungstic acid molecules combine with hydrogen peroxide to form a peroxide which does not exist as sol, but remains dissolved as a true solution. The molecule of this peroxide compound may, like molecules of hydrogen peroxide, react with formaldehyde to give rise to formic acid and behave also as molecules of hydrogen peroxide in the process of iodometric titration. It is only the sol of tungstic acid which presents a

photo-sensitive surface, on which may be fixed by adsorption a molecule of hydrogen peroxide, or a molecule of tungstic acid, which in their turn, react with formaldehyde under stimulus of light. The evidence in favour of the formation of tungstic acid molecule, by reaction of tungstic acid with hydrogen peroxide, has been furnished by Pissarjewsky (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, **43**, 166). He determined the distribution of hydrogen peroxide between ether and an aqueous solution of sodium tungstate and sulphuric acid and concluded that a considerable amount of hydrogen peroxide remained combined with tungstic acid in aqueous solution. We, therefore, postulate that a molecule of hydrogen peroxide combines with a molecule of sodium tungstate to form a molecule of tungstic acid.

If the dissociation constant k' of the tungstic acid is small, then it follows that—

$$(a) \quad \text{For } C_{\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4} > C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$$

the concentration of tungstic acid as such = $C_{\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4} - C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$.

$$(b) \quad \text{For } C_{\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4} = C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$$

the concentration of tungstic acid = $\sqrt{k' \cdot C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}}$.

$$(c) \quad \text{For } C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} > C_{\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4}$$

the concentration of tungstic acid = $\frac{k' \cdot C_{\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4}}{C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2} - C_{\text{H}_2\text{WO}_4}}$.

Since the value of k' is small, it is clear that for a definite initial concentration of tungstic acid, the quantity of tungstic acid existing in colloidal state will continually diminish as the concentration of hydrogen peroxide is increased, but at values of equivalent concentration, the diminution will be extremely rapid. Now, on the very reasonable assumption that it is the tungstic acid sol that is photo-sensitive, we are in a position to explain the observed sudden diminution of the velocity constant, when the concentration of hydrogen peroxide becomes equivalent to that of sodium tungstate.

Beyond this transition point, the concentration of tungstic acid existing as such, becomes very small and its rate of diminution with further increase in the concentration of hydrogen peroxide becomes much less, and the curve of velocity constants becomes necessarily flat again.

We are also now in a position to explain the other features of this reaction. It is well-known that particles of a tungstic acid sol are negatively charged and hydrogen ions will therefore be electrically adsorbed on the surface. According to Mukherjee (*Trans. Farad. Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103) the fraction θ of the original charge on the surface not neutralised by adsorption of monovalent ions is given by the following equation—

$$k_2 C \theta^2 + \theta - 1 = 0$$

where C is the concentration of monovalent ion. Now, if θ be small compared with unity, that is, if the neutralisation of charge is almost complete, which we may expect when the concentration of hydrogen ion is not too small,

$$\theta^2 = \frac{1}{k_2 C} \quad \text{or} \quad \theta = \frac{k_3}{\sqrt{C_H}}$$

If θ is the fraction of the charge not neutralised by hydrogen ions, it follows that θ also represents the fraction of the total surface of sol particles, which remains available for adsorption by other molecular species. We have already postulated that molecules of hydrogen peroxide or pertungstic acid can be adsorbed on the surface of tungstic acid sol particles. The amount of adsorption complex so formed will be proportional to the concentration of peroxide (free hydrogen peroxide + peroxide of tungstic acid) and the free surface or θ_1 (fraction of surface covered with peroxide) = $k_3 \cdot C_{H_2O_2} \cdot \frac{k_2}{\sqrt{C_H}}$.

This relation is true only when the concentration of peroxide is not very large compared with the concentration of the sol. If the concentration of peroxide is very large, then the whole of the available surface θ will be covered with peroxide and we shall be dealing with a saturated surface.

$$\text{Here } \theta_1 = \theta = \frac{k_3}{\sqrt{C_H}}$$

The elementary spaces of the surface covered with hydrogen peroxide or pertungstic acid get activated under the stimulus of radiation and may oxidise a molecule of formaldehyde which happens to collide against this surface during its life-period of excitation. If τ be the life-period of this excited peroxide spaces, and T be the interval between two successive collisions of formaldehyde molecules on the same peroxide space, the velocity of oxidation of formaldehyde will be given by the following equations—the intensity of effective radiation remaining constant.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_4 \cdot \frac{\tau}{T + \tau} \cdot \theta_1.$$

The interval between two successive collisions of the formaldehyde molecules against the peroxide surface will be inversely proportional to the concentration of formaldehyde.

Hence

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\tau}{\frac{A}{C_{\text{formaldehyde}}} + \tau} \cdot k_4 \cdot k_3 \cdot k_2 \cdot \frac{C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}}{\sqrt{C_{\text{H}}}} \quad \text{for lower conc. of } \text{H}_2\text{O}_2.$$

$$\text{and } \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{\tau}{\frac{A}{C_{\text{formaldehyde}}} + \tau} \cdot k_4 \cdot \frac{k_3}{\sqrt{C_{\text{H}}}} \quad \text{for very large conc. of } \text{H}_2\text{O}_2.$$

If T or $A/C_{\text{formaldehyde}}$ be small compared with τ ,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_5 \cdot \frac{C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}}{\sqrt{C_{\text{H}}}} \quad \text{for lower conc. of } \text{H}_2\text{O}_2,$$

$$\text{and } \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k_6}{\sqrt{C_{\text{H}}}} \quad \text{for large conc. of } \text{H}_2\text{O}_2.$$

That is, for lower concentration of hydrogen peroxide, we have a unimolecular reaction whose velocity varies inversely as the square root of concentration of hydrogen. For large concentrations of hydrogen peroxide, the reaction tends to be zero-molecular.

It will also be noticed that the function $\frac{\tau}{\frac{A}{C_{\text{formaldehyde}}} + \tau}$

is included in the values of k_5 or k_6 and $1/k_5$ or $1/k_6$ will therefore, include the expression,

$$\frac{\tau + \frac{A}{C_{\text{formaldehyde}}}}{\tau} \quad \text{or} \quad 1 + \frac{A}{\tau} = \frac{1}{C_{\text{formaldehyde}}}$$

It is therefore to be expected, that other conditions remaining the same, the inverse of velocity constant plotted against the inverse of the concentration of formaldehyde should be a straight line. This has been found approximately to be the case.

The values (between two and seven) for quantum efficiency of the reaction, indicate that there exists a chain mechanism for the reaction, but that the length of the chain is quite small. The small temperature coefficient of the reaction also indicates that the nature of the dark reaction chains following the primary photochemical process is fairly simple. It is, however, premature at this stage to attempt to postulate the exact nature of the chain mechanism.

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